

Studies on *s*-Triazinyl Compounds as Potential Medicinal Agents. Part II.

(Miss) J. N. ACHARYA, R. R. ASTIK and K. A. THAKER

University Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar

Manuscript received 22 September 1975 ; revised 17 November 1975 ; accepted 20 November 1975

In continuation of our previous work*, we have prepared several *s*-triazinyl derivatives of benzocaine by the condensation of 2,4-dichloro-6-(2-phenetidino)-*s*-triazine with benzocaine in acetone and the product on further reaction with aliphatic, aromatic and heterocyclic amines gave 2-alkyl/aryl/heterocyclyl amino-4-(4-carbethoxy anilino)-6-(2-phenetidino)-*s*-triazines.

PHENETIDINES and their derivatives have a marked antitubercular, bacteriostatic and antipyretic activity.¹⁻⁶ Besides being a well-known local anaesthetic⁷, benzocaine is also reported to possess antibacterial, fungicidal and antitubercular activity.⁸⁻¹¹ We have prepared *s*-triazine derivatives of the type,

where R_1 and R_2 are alkyl, aryl or are parts of a heterocyclic base. These compounds are prepared to test their antibacterial properties and to study them as medicinal agents since *s*-triazinyl derivatives are reported as possessing antibacterial, fungicidal, insecticidal and antimalarial properties.¹²⁻¹⁵

MOLECULAR SIZE

Experimental

Preparation of 2-(4-carbethoxy anilino)-4-(2-phenetidino)-6-chloro-*s*-triazines (II) :

A solution of benzocaine (0.01 *M*) in acetone was added dropwise to a mechanically stirred solution of 2,4-dichloro-6-(2-phenetidino)-*s*-triazine (I)¹⁶ (0.01 *M*) in acetone during 30 min and stirred at 35°-45° for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was maintained alkaline throughout the reaction by the addition of 4 *N* aqueous NaOH. The mixture at room temperature was poured into ice-water and 4 *N* HCl added till it was acidic to congo-red. The product was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, m. p. 180°.

Found : N 16.67%

$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{ClN}_5\text{O}_3$. Required : N 16.92%

Preparation of 2-alkyl|aryl|heterocyclyl amino-4-(4-carbethoxy anilino)-6-(2-phenetidino)-*s*-triazines (III) :

The amine (0.002 *M*) in dioxane (20 ml) was added to 2-(4-carbethoxy anilino)-4-(2-phenetidino)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (0.002 *M*) in the same solvent. The reaction mixture was heated at 60°-70° for 3 hr while being maintained alkaline by the addition of 1 *N* aqueous NaOH. The cooled mixture was poured in ice-water and acidified with 4 *N* HCl (congo-red). The product was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. The physical and analytical data of these compounds are given in Table 1.

*Accepted for publication in this Journal. Paper No. 173/75, dated 12-8-1975.

TABLE 1—COMPOUNDS OF THE TYPE (III)

Sr. No.	R ₁ ^a	R ₂ ^a	Molecular Formula	m.p. °C	Reqd.	% N Found
1.	H	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₈	193 (d)	20.59	20.73
2.	H	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₈	211 (d)	19.91	19.86
3.	H	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₈	235 (d)	19.27	19.05
4.	H	n-C ₄ H ₉	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₈	315 (d)	18.66	18.81
5.	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₈	212 (d)	19.91	19.94
6.	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₈	205 (d)	18.66	18.71
7.	n-C ₃ H ₇	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₂₆ H ₃₄ N ₆ O ₈	250 (d)	17.58	17.43
8.	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	n-C ₅ H ₁₁	C ₃₀ H ₄₂ N ₆ O ₈	240	15.26	15.61
9.	H	HOCH ₂ CH ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₈	260 (d)	19.18	19.07
10.	HOCH ₂ CH ₂	HOCH ₂ CH ₂	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₈	245 (d)	17.43	17.65
11.	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₈	230 (d)	17.87	18.12
12.	H	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ ClN ₆ O ₈	232	16.65	16.52
13.	H	3-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ ClN ₆ O ₈	251	16.65	16.71
14.	H	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ ClN ₆ O ₈	233 (d)	16.65	16.84
15.	H	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₈	185	17.36	17.05
16.	H	3-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₈	170	17.36	17.51
17.	H	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₈	229 (d)	17.36	17.43
18.	H	2-CH ₃ .O.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₈	145	16.80	17.02
19.	H	4-CH ₃ .O.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₈	220	16.80	17.11
20.	H	2-O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₇ O ₈	221 (d)	19.03	19.25
21.	H	3-O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₇ O ₈	231 (d)	19.03	18.92
22.	H	4-O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₇ O ₈	220 (d)	19.03	19.31
23.	H	2, 5-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₈	210 (d)	15.59	15.76
24.	H	4-Br.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ BrN ₆ O ₈	202 (d)	15.30	15.17
25.	H	3-HO.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₈	186 (d)	17.29	17.42
26.	H	4-HO.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₈	218 (d)	17.29	17.18
27.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₈	131	17.36	17.61
28.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ CH ₂	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₈	192	16.87	17.20
29.	H	2-C ₂ H ₅ O.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₈	174 (d)	16.34	16.13
30.	H	C ₆ H ₁₁	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₈	185	17.64	17.85
31.	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₈	198	17.36	17.62
32.	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₈	196 (d)	16.87	16.92
33.	H	4-H ₂ C ₂ OOC.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₉ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₈	256 (d)	15.50	15.41
34.	H	4-CH ₃ .CONH.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₈ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄	192 (d)	18.60	18.87
35.	H	4-(1, 3-C ₄ H ₇ N ₂ .HNO ₂ S).C ₆ H ₄	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ N ₉ O ₅ S	220 (d)	20.09	20.01
36.	H	4-(1, 3-C ₃ H ₇ NS.HNO ₂ S).C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₇ H ₂₉ N ₉ O ₅ S	257	21.32	21.56
37.	H	4-(1, 3-C ₄ H ₉ NS.HNO ₂ S).C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₉ H ₂₈ N ₉ O ₅ S ₂	226	17.72	17.95
38.	H	4-(1, 3-C ₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ .CH ₂ HNO ₂ S).C ₆ H ₄	C ₃₁ H ₃₁ N ₉ O ₅ S	255 (d)	19.65	19.82
39.	-N<R ₁ R ₂	= C ₄ H ₈ NO	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₈ O ₄	257	18.10	18.09
40.	-N<R ₁ R ₂	= C ₅ H ₁₀ N	C ₂₅ H ₃₀ N ₈ O ₄	215 (d)	18.19	18.37

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Saurashtra University for providing research facilities and to CSIR, New Delhi, for junior research fellowships to J. N. A. and R. R. A.

References

1. B. L. FREEDLANDER and A. FURST, *Wasmann J. Biol.*, 1951, **9**, 355; *Chem. Abs.*, 1952, **46**, 8772 d.
2. R. NODZU, H. WATANABE, S. OKA, C. NAGAISHI, T. TERAMATSU, H. ARIMA, M. KOGAME and K. KOBAYASHI, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1951, **71**, 713.
3. T. ISHIBASHI, *Nippon Yakurigaku Zasshi.*, 1956, **52**, 215; *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, **51**, 13208 i.
4. Y. HIMENO, T. HATATSU, K. ARISAWA, S. KOSHIMURA and R. HIRATA, *Ann. Rept. Research Inst. Tuberc.*, Kanazawa University, 1954, **12**, 5; *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, **49**, 9159 g.
5. H. HUELLER, K. D. LUESS, H. WOLLMANN, R. POHLO-
UDEK-FABINI, *Pharmazie*, 1968, **23**, 188.
6. H. WAHLIG, H. M. HENNING, L. HEPDING and H. J. BERTRAM, *Arzneimittel-Forsch.*, 1962, **12**, 1123.
7. H. C. BRILL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1320.
8. A. MOREL, A. ROCHAIX and H. DELABORDE, *Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1935, **49**, 612.
9. H. BLOCH, H. LEHR and H. ERLLENMEYER, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1945, **28**, 1406.
10. K. I. MELVILLE and K. L. STEHLE, *Canad. J. Res.*, 1944, **22**, E, 95.
11. D. CURTIS, U. S. P. 2, 385, 262, Sept. 18, 1945; *Chem. Abs.*, 1945, **39**, 5414⁸.
12. C. N. WOLF, U. S. P. 2, 720, 480, Oct. 11, 1955; *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, **50**, 13101 b.
13. C. N. WOLF, P. H. SCHULDT and M. M. BALSWIN, *Science*, 1935, **121**, 61.
14. Imperial Chemical Industries Ltd., *Belg.*, 610, 139, May 9, 1962, *Brit. appl. Nov.* 11, 1960, p. 9; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, **57**, 12962 c).
15. E. W. CUTHBERTSON and J. S. MOFFATT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 561; F. H. S. CURD, J. K. LANDQUIST and F. L. ROSE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 154.
16. H. P. BURCHFIELD and E. E. STORRS, *Nature*, 1960, **187**, 593.